

Urban Relief

Athens Pilot Report

D4.4

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Short description	The Athens pilot Report documents the preparation, design and progress of the three campaigns that are implemented for the Athens pilot by DAEM in collaboration with NOA, CIBOS and ICCS. The citizen science campaigns focus on: the air quality monitoring, the heat discomfort by extreme climate conditions in Athens during the summer period and finally, the development of an updated tree registry for the city.
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Acronyms

ACSM	Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor
BC	Black carbon
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
CS	Citizen Science
EEA	European Environment Agency
GPS	Global Positioning System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LEZ	Low Emission Zone
LoRa	Long Range
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
OPC	Optical Particle Counting
PANACEA	PANhellenic infrastructure for Atmospheric Composition and climatE chAnge
PM	Particulate Matter
QR	Quick Response
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SMPS	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer
TRH	Temperature and Relevant Humidity
UB	Urban Background
UFP	Ultrafine Particles
UG	Urban Green

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Executive Summary

The purpose of the Deliverable 4.4 “Athens Pilot Report” is to provide a detailed and comprehensive overview of the pilot activities in the field of climate mitigation and adaptation. The Athens pilot designs and implements the activities taking place under the themes of air quality, heat discomfort and trees’ mapping. Hence, this report mainly documents the progress of the three campaigns and the main findings. Since Urban Releaf is a citizen science project, the main target is citizens’ participation under diverse groups, such as students, city employees, residents of Athens etc. These diverse citizen groups are engaged in running relevant campaigns to tackle environmental issues.

Subsequently, the report describes the background of the pilot as well as the design, implementation and progress of all the campaigns as well as feedback received. Next steps and further planning are also outlined toward the completion of the campaigns and to meet the challenges set up by the city of Athens for climate mitigation.

This report, as it is submitted at the first period of the project, focuses mainly on the Heat Stress campaign and analysis that is already completed and interesting outcomes are pointed out. Also, the Air quality campaign is reported and its status includes already collected important data by sensors installed in several municipal areas and also through mobile monitoring. Finally, the outcomes of the trees campaign will be reported in more detail in the next reporting period, since up to now, preparatory activities in terms of designing, mobile application development and scheduling have been completed.

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Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspaces, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making, as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand the current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process.

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1 Air Quality Campaign

The first campaign that DAEM designed in the Athens pilot implementation is the installation of low-cost sensors distributed by NOA to assess air quality (PM_{2.5}) in the city of Athens. The main scope of this campaign is to enhance the AQ monitoring network of PANACEA Research Infrastructure by increasing the spatiotemporal resolution in the Municipality of Athens, which is the largest and most densely populated in Greece, and, therefore, the centre of attention for the exposure of a large part of the Greek population. The densification of the network in Athens was also a strategic goal in the PANACEA infrastructure development plans.

The second air quality case study carried out by NOA aims to map citizen exposure to ambient particle pollution, focusing on mobile monitoring of crucial “new” pollutants that are emerging in EU air quality management legislation, namely Black Carbon (BC) and Ultrafine Particles (UFP). Their concentrations were measured during pedestrian campaigns, with emphasis on highlighting contrasts across different exposure micro-environments and exploring the benefits of urban greenspaces. The basic context, as mentioned below in detail, is the provision of air quality sensors and data at a local level and mainly at areas where different types of citizen groups are active, indicatively medical centres that target the whole area population, parks that attract both residents and visitors, schools where the audience is the school community etc.

1.1 Context and Objectives

The local challenges for Athens intercorrelate in terms of environmental conditions, as the recent increasing temperatures and heatwave incidents have also a countereffect on the air quality indexes¹ and vice versa. Hence, the city aims at increasing its resilience in heatwaves (liaison with TRH campaign) and taking measures to reduce them (liaison with Trees campaign). The joint effects of heat stress and air pollution are a perennial concern in Athens, especially during high-summer conditions. The recent environmental policies and climate contract that Athens has structured and committed to highlight the importance of air quality improvement. The latter will take place by a top-down approach, with the adoption of city measures, but also by increasing the density, frequency and quality of pollutant concentration data collection, as well as raising awareness among citizens on the issue.

Hence, the Athens pilot exploits the national **PANhellenic infrastructure for Atmospheric Composition and climatE chAnge (PANACEA)** as a network of trustworthy and high-quality calibrated sensors and the existing knowledge base on atmospheric composition and solar radiation variations, which have been extensively characterized and are continuously monitored through the research infrastructures of NOA. The targeted AQ metric is PM_{2.5}, which is recognized as the regulated pollutant with the most important health effects and a verified causal link with high rates of premature mortality. So, the objective of the air quality campaign is threefold:

- Densify the PANACEA PM_{2.5} sensor and data network within the Municipality of Athens and conduct better exposure assessment for a larger fraction of the local population.
- Raise public awareness about air quality and its effects on public health.
- To correlate the data collected in research analysis with the other two campaigns for a complete environmental output for Athens.

¹ Mavrakis, A., Kapsali, A., Tsiros, I.X. et al. Air quality and meteorological patterns of an early spring heatwave event in an industrialized area of Attica, Greece. Euro-Mediterr J Environ Integr 6, 25 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41207-020-00237-0>

1.2 Design and Implementation

PM_{2.5} monitoring network

To tackle these objectives, the air quality campaign was thoroughly designed and prepared with the collaboration of DAEM, NOA and city representatives, following internal meetings and strong communication. The design foresaw the installation of PurpleAir PA-II sensor-based monitors, in all 7 municipal districts of the City of Athens (Figure 1).

Figure 1. 7 Municipal Districts of Athens

The methodology for obtaining a dense network called for installing monitoring devices in multiple municipal buildings and spaces for each district. The scope was to install them in public buildings and open areas that gather citizens, residents and the public visiting the locations to request municipal services and other leisure amenities. The design of the network took into consideration the existing EU air quality macro-siting and micro-siting guidelines (EU 2881/2024 Directive) for spatially representative measurements, but also the specific goals of Urban ReLeaf in the thematic of Urban Greening and Urban Resilience. Each of the 7 districts was planned to include one sensor from each of the following 4 site types:

- **Traffic (T)** - Site located in a major traffic avenue, at a short distance from the road and at heights not exceeding 7m
- **Near Traffic (NT)** - Site located at more than 50m from a major road (e.g. a building or venue) in a residential area.
- **Near Green (NG)** - Site located at a short distance (less than 1 km, ideally up to 100 m) from the border of an urban greenspace (Figure 2)
- **Urban Green (UG)** - Site inside a large urban greenspace, such as a park or another public leisure area

Figure 2. Typical NG location of the 5th Municipal District, at the 3rd Nursery School of Athens.

Pedestrian monitoring campaigns for emerging pollutants (UFP, BC)

The second pillar of air quality monitoring in the Athens pilot refers to the mobile monitoring of emerging particle pollutants in high spatiotemporal resolution, providing real-time mapping of traffic, urban and greenspace exposure effects. Mobile monitoring was conducted by pedestrian mapping along predefined routes, with multiple repetitions to increase the reliability and representativeness of results. Pedestrian mapping provides flexibility in characterizing differences among different exposure microenvironments, from high-traffic roadways to urban greenspaces, with precise spatial analysis thanks to the low walking speed. Ultrafine particles (UFP) and Black carbon (BC) and ultrafine particles (UFPs) are some of the pollutants responsible for severe health effects, and they can both be reliably measured using miniaturized portable instruments.

The aim was to monitor the pollutant concentrations along two predesigned routes (National Garden and Field of Mars) in the center of Athens, performing morning and evening measurements every day for three consecutive weeks during summer conditions. Each route was designed to contain traffic (TR), urban background (UB) and urban green (UG) segments. Both routes included a traffic segment along primary high-density traffic roads, a lower-exposure residential zone, and a large urban park. The main differences between the two routes were that the TR segment around the National Garden is located within a low emission zone (LEZ) with relatively lower traffic loads, the UB residential segment around the Field of Mars is more socio-economically challenged, and that the UG segment of the National Garden is in the core of the park, unlike at the Field of Mars, which circles near the border of the greenspace. The two routes are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The designed routes for the pedestrian campaigns. (a) Field of Mars and (b) National Garden, where orange line represents the traffic (TR) segment, the blue line refers to the urban background (UB) residential area, and the green line represents the urban greenspace (UG).

1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The areas and locations of the municipal buildings and greenspaces within the Athens municipal boundaries, where $PM_{2.5}$ monitors would be placed, were identified in a detailed meeting in February 2024 between the research team of NOA, DAEM - that would be responsible for the installation - and the Municipality of Athens represented by the Directors of the Decentralization and Administration Agency. Then, the City provided all the necessary information for each building and area, namely the type of building, the exact location, the audience it attracts etc., following internal communication with the relevant person in charge. Finally, this preparational phase resulted in structuring a list with the identified locations, including also suitable alternatives. The list also included the address information, the number of the municipal district, the type of location (T, NT, UG or NG), a comment on the exact position where each device was proposed to be installed and finally the credentials of the Wi-Fi connection of each venue that were essential for the connection of the monitor. In a few cases there are existing PANACEA-network monitors at sites in the municipality, hence additional installation was not necessary. Also, it must be noted that there was a requirement for the position of the sensors in traffic buildings, namely the sensor should be installed at maximum the 2nd floor so that there is small distance from the traffic road and in the facade of the building that faces the traffic (Figure 4). For the rest of the categories (NT, UG, NG) there was not such prerequisite, hence the exact position was decided in collaboration with the building responsible person.

Figure 4. T location of the 4th Municipal District at the administrative offices of the district.

In total this exercise resulted in 40 candidate locations being considered, including both primary alternatives in the 7 districts. After additional internal collaboration of DAEM with the City of Athens and each venue responsible, 27 locations were shortlisted. One was missing since for the 4th district of Athens there was not near traffic location that could tackle the prerequisites of the analysis. More detailed the 27 points included:

- The buildings of **6 municipal schools** (nursery schools)
- **11 administrative buildings** of the municipality with high number of visitors. Indicatively there can be mentioned: the Municipal Veterinarian centre, the offices of the City of Athens Reception and Solidarity Center (Figure 5), Municipal Medical Centers providing first level medical support to residents, the Center for Combating Gender-based Violence and Multiple Discrimination, administrative offices located in each district etc (Figure 6)
- **7 green areas** of the city including the NOA Thissio Supersite where a sensor was already installed, the premises of the Department of Athens for Greening that is located in a vast green area, the Lycabettus Hill, the National Garden of Athens etc.
- Finally, there are also **3 locations covered by the PANACEA network** (Figure 7) , with installations complimentary to Urban ReLeaf.

Figure 5. T location of the 1st Municipal District at the City of Athens Reception and Solidarity Center.

Figure 6. NT location of the 6th Municipal District at the Center for Combating Gender-based Violence and Multiple Discrimination.

Figure 7 PANACEA AQ sensors operating in the Greater Athens' area.

Subsequently, DAEM performed audits in the 11 administrative buildings to acquire the necessary permissions from the people in charge of the buildings. Another audit took place by DAEM with an electrician for the electrical requirements of the devices and one colleague to ensure that the Wi-Fi credentials were valid and/or to install Wi-Fi connections in buildings that where it was not available. The monitors were then mounted in the locations by a municipality electrician and then connected to Wi-Fi by DAEM to send data and visualise them in near-real time by the open-access air-quality.gr online platform. For the installation sites a template was shared by NOA as “Site Characterization Form” (Appendix A) and then completed by DAEM for each of the locations with specific details on the installation.

The same procedure was repeated for installations at 11 municipal schools that required also an additional approval by the Directorate of Municipal Nursery Schools of Athens. Finally, for the installation of the sensors in green areas a part of actions were undertaken by NOA on the National Garden, the Lycabetus Hill and the Athens Department of Greening.

In total the current progress of the Athens air quality campaign (installation of equipment acquired within Urban ReLeaf) includes: 17 installed sensors in buildings (6 schools and 11 other buildings) and 5 sensors in green areas. The pending point is the installation in 2 green areas that have already been identified.

For PM_{2.5} monitoring in Urban ReLeaf, the PurpleAir PA-II sensor-based monitor was selected (Figure 8). The PA-II is a small size (85 x 125 mm), lightweight (< 0.5 kg), and waterproof instrument. It was designed for outdoor use in CS applications since citizens can easily install it at locations like balconies and rooftops, provided the availability of mains power and Wi-Fi. The device can report data in near-real time, with a minimum data update frequency of 2 minutes, and through its Wi-Fi connectivity transmits directly those measurements over the internet, to the PurpleAir Inc. cloud-based servers and air-quality.gr platform. A PA-II monitor consists of a pair of twin Plantower PMS5003 sensors, which is an optical particle counting system (OPC) that uses a laser light source. The PA-II device also includes a Bosch Sensortec BME 280 sensor for temperature, relative humidity, and barometric pressure.

Figure 8. Side view (a) and bottom view (b) of the PurpleAir PA-II air quality monitor, containing two Plantower PMS5003 optical particle counting (OPC) sensors.

The performance of the PA-II device in $PM_{2.5}$ measurement is characterized by high inter-device repeatability (precision) and high correlations with reference instruments concurrently operating at the same locations. These characteristics allow for the calibration of its outputs to improve the accuracy of $PM_{2.5}$ measurements and limit the influence of intrinsic and extrinsic factors such as particle size distribution, composition-dependent particle hygroscopicity, and refractive indices, episodic emissions causing high concentrations (e.g. smog events, wildfires) and atmospheric humidity.

The evaluation and calibration of air quality instruments were performed by the comparison to collocated and simultaneously operating reference instruments. The calibration for all sensors was carried out at the NOA Thissio Supersite (Figure 9). A reference-equivalent beta attenuation monitors for $PM_{2.5}$ (Thermo-Fisher 5014i, CEN 14907:2005) was used for comparisons and evaluation. Additional instruments were used to scientifically explore the physicochemical aspects that determine the PA-II performance, including a 31-channel (0.28-35 μm) high-performance OPC providing particle number and mass concentration distributions (Grimm 11D).

Figure 9. (a) Collocated PurpleAir PA-II devices being calibrated at the NOA Thissio Supersite, (b) Comparison of pooled sensor concentrations with concentrations of a collocated reference monitor during calibration.

The calibration procedure for 25 sensors took place in three phases (calibration for at least three weeks per phase). The devices were placed at the station in two masts, in close proximity to the sampling line of the reference instrument (Figure 9a) Regarding the repeatability of the method, comparisons between PA-II monitors showed almost perfect linearity, with the R^2 coefficients of determination in the linear regression lines being above 0.95. The comparison of the average $PM_{2.5}$ values from the sensors with the reference instrument, apart from the

high correlation (Figure 9b), indicates the existence of a systematic error, as the slope is less than unity and there is a positive intercept.

The devices selected for the mobile campaign were the MA200 micro-aethalometer and the Naneos Partector 2, for BC and UFPs, respectively (Figure 10). The portable MA200 multi-wavelength micro-aethalometer was used for BC in mobile pedestrian campaigns. The MA200 monitor presents high intra-device repeatability and excellent collinearity to reference-grade AE33 desktop aethalometers. It is a low-weight, small-sized photometer that can be easily carried by a pedestrian mapper. Measurements were collected at a frequency of 10 seconds. The MA200 aethalometers used in the pedestrian campaign were calibrated at the NOA supersite in Thissio, through comparison with an AE33 aethalometer and a Multi-Angle Absorption Photometer.

For measurements of ultrafine particles (particles with diameters below 100 nm), a Naneos Partector 2 UFP electrometric counter/sizer was used, which is the instrument of choice in the majority of new mobile characterization studies. The Partector 2 is a lightweight and compact battery-powered instrument. It has the advantage of not containing working fluids for magnifying and counting individual particles, providing substantial flexibility in pedestrian measurements. The monitor provides simultaneous measurements of UFP particle number concentration, particle diameter, and lung-deposited surface area (LDSA). Data are displayed in real time on a graphical display and are averaged at 10-second intervals in the analysis of mapping results. Partector 2 devices were calibrated before the implementation of the pedestrian campaign in Athens, in concurrent operation with a research-grade Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) (TSI 3088 coupled with a TSI 3025 Condensation Particle Counter) operating at the NOA Thissio supersite.

Figure 10. MA200 micro-aethalometer (on the left) measuring black carbon and Naneos Partector 2 (on the right) measuring ultrafine particles.

1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

The citizen engagement of the air quality campaign is centred around the users of each building; hence it refers to a wide range and different types of end users. The citizens are not engaged by distributing sensors to them, but rather through:

- awareness raising activities,
- information sessions,
- insight campaigns on the measured data,
- interpretation of the results as valuable findings for their daily life etc.

So far, the air quality campaign is focused on the deployment of sensors and in the next period of the project such activities will be designed and tailored according to the audience.

The areas of installation have diverse types of audience, indicatively mentioned:

- Students at the nursery schools and teachers
- Municipal employees and citizens visiting the administrative offices for example: the municipal medical centres, the offices for social solidarity, the municipal veterinarian, the districts' administrative offices etc (Figure 11)
- Visitors to green areas and parks etc.

Figure 11. T location of the 3rd Municipal District at the Municipal Medical Center.

Currently, the engagement activities are not yet fully structured; however, the planned approach includes on-site meetings with citizens and employees to present and explain the data collected to date. Additional information will be provided on the impact of air pollution on quality of life. Educational visits will also be organized in nursery schools for students, in collaboration with teachers. Furthermore, an informational printed campaign will be implemented at the installation sites, including leaflets, posters, and other communication materials.

1.5 Findings and Reflections

Results from the PM_{2.5} monitoring network

The PM_{2.5} network has been operational since November 16, 2024, providing near real-time measurements with high data coverage. Results from the hourly concentration times series of

18 PurpleAir monitors were analysed. The locations of these sites are displayed in Figure 12 below:

Figure 12. The PM_{2.5} sensor network in Athens by site type.

The data are collected and processed by NOA on a weekly basis, and the operation of monitors is also tracked, with prompt action by DAEM and NOA in case of offline or malfunctioning devices. After almost a year of operation of the sensor network (November 2024 – October 2025), indicative results are provided for each type of location. Table 1 provides the relevant information on monitor and location names (in the way they are displayed online on the [PurpleAir map](#) and the [air-quality.gr](#) platform). The coverage values (valid hourly and daily measurements) are also provided. For the hourly values, annual data completeness was 50% or higher at 16 out of 18 sites.

Table 1. Information about AQ monitors and installation sites.

Device Name	Location Name	Site Type	Installation Date	Coverage (hourly) *	Coverage (valid 24-hours) **
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_01	ATHENS-PSYRRI	NT	26/09/2024	31%	31%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_02	ATHENS-GOUDI	T	20/11/2024	61%	60%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_03	ATHENS-KOLONOS	T	14/11/2024	50%	49%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_05	ATHENS-KYPSELI	T	14/11/2024	96%	95%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_06	ATHENS-OMONOIA	T	26/09/2024	69%	69%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_07	ATHENS-A. PATISSIA	NT	14/11/2024	98%	97%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_08	ATHENS-PAGKRATI	T	22/11/2024	98%	97%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_09	ATHENS-PL. AMERIKIS	NT	14/11/2024	100%	99%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_10	ATHENS-GAZI	T	26/09/2024	72%	72%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_11	ATHENS-PETRALONA	NT	15/11/2024	97%	97%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_12	ATHENS-PROBONA	NG	22/07/2025	58%	59%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_15	ATHENS-NEAPOLI	NG	12/05/2025	98%	99%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_16	ATHENS-ABELOKIPOI	NT	22/07/2025	59%	59%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_17	ATHENS-PAGKRATI2	NG	13/05/2025	99%	99%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_19	ATHENS-K. PATISSIA	T	22/07/2025	59%	59%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_20	ATHENS-PETRALONA2	NG	12/05/2025	99%	99%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_21	ATHENS-SEPOLIA	NG	22/07/2025	30%	30%
PANACEA_URBAN_RELEAF_23	ATHENS-DIEFTHINSI PRASINOU	UG	11/07/2025	50%	50%

*The coverage rates refer to the period November 2024 – October 2025.

**A 24-hour average concentration is considered valid when calculated from at least 18 (75%) valid hourly concentrations (EU) 2024/2881.

Descriptive statistics of the PM_{2.5} levels recorded at the network measurement sites during the first year (November 2024 – October 2025) of operation are presented below (Table 2). The presented statistics are based on valid 24-hour average concentrations, calculated from the calibrated hourly concentrations (with a completeness criterion of 18 valid values per 24-hour period). Each monitor had its own calibration equation applied. The average concentration exceeded 10 µg m⁻³ at all measurement sites (even those that had only warm period measurements in 2025). It is noted that this is the newly promulgated annual limit value in the EU legislation (EU 2881/2024 directive).

According to EU Directive 2024/2881, the 24-hour limit value for PM_{2.5} is set at 25 µg m⁻³, which should not be exceeded more than 18 times in a calendar year. The results of

measurements during the first-year show that 10 sites (i.e. all the sites that started operating in 2024) exceeded this threshold, which indicates that compliance with the new AQ standards for the municipality of Athens (which should be assessed by reference measurements at regulatory stations) will be difficult.

In addition to establishing a 24-hour limit value for PM_{2.5}, the new EU directive, for the first time, provides for the monitoring of prolonged episodic concentrations of particulate matter, and sets alert and information thresholds for the population. For PM_{2.5}, the alert (and population information) threshold is defined as a 24-hour average concentration above 50 µg m⁻³ and monitored on a three-day basis. In case of three consecutive days with average concentrations above 50 µg m⁻³ an alert is created. During the measurement period, 7 violations of the alert threshold were observed, related to excessive residential biomass burning, and lasting from 4 to 5 consecutive days (31/12/2024 – 04/01/2025).

Table 2. Statistics on the concentrations recorded by the installed network (18 sensors) during the first year of operation (November 2024 – October 2025).

Location Name	Average ± standard deviation	Maximum 24-hour average concentration	Number of days with 24-hour average concentration > 25 µg m ⁻³	Number of days with 24-hour average concentration > 15 µg m ⁻³
ATHENS-PSYRRI	25.0 ± 14.0	104	42 (39%)	87 (81%)
ATHENS-GOUDI	15.2 ± 6.4	43	16 (8%)	88 (42%)
ATHENS-KOLONOS	20.8 ± 12.9	73	47 (27%)	104 (61%)
ATHENS-KYPSELI	18.6 ± 11.0	99	61 (18%)	171 (51%)
ATHENS-OMONIOIA	15.2 ± 6.5	43	19 (8%)	102 (42%)
ATHENS-A. PATISSIA	16.6 ± 11.4	80	53 (16%)	136 (40%)
ATHENS-PAGKRATI	13.1 ± 6.0	43	19 (6%)	99 (29%)
ATHENS-PL. AMERIKIS	18.0 ± 12.0	100	60 (17%)	163 (47%)
ATHENS-GAZI	20.9 ± 13.3	94	64 (25%)	144 (57%)
ATHENS-PETRALONA	16.5 ± 10.5	93	45 (13%)	136 (40%)
ATHENS-PROBONA	10.4 ± 3.4	20	0 (%)	10 (10%)
ATHENS-NEAPOLI	10.5 ± 3.2	20	0 (%)	18 (11%)
ATHENS-ABELOKIPOI	10.6 ± 3.3	19	0 (%)	11 (11%)
ATHENS-PAGKRATI2	10.7 ± 3.3	20	0 (%)	18 (11%)
ATHENS-K. PATISSIA	11.5 ± 3.7	22	0 (%)	20 (20%)
ATHENS-PETRALONA2	11.0 ± 3.3	20	0 (%)	22 (13%)
ATHENS-SEPOLIA	11.0 ± 4.1	21	0 (%)	11 (21%)
ATHENS-DIEFTHINSI PRASINOU	13.7 ± 10.2	84	18 (10%)	44 (25%)

The concentration intervals (µg m⁻³) for air quality characterization in relation to PM_{2.5} used by the European Environment Agency (EEA) are: 0-10: Good, 10-20: Fair, 20-25: Moderate, 25-50: Poor, 50-75: Very Poor, >75: Extremely Poor. Figure 13 summarizes the air quality

characterization results for Athens in relation to PM_{2.5} levels, as assessed by applying the EEA air quality index to the 24-hour rolling average hourly concentrations. Based on the time series of hourly values of the 18 measurement sites, air quality was considered good or fair in above 40% of cases at all sites. However, there were 8 sites where AQ was characterized as bad or worse for 10% or more study period hours.

Figure 13. Distribution of PM_{2.5} concentrations in air quality categories for the measurement period in Athens. The assessment is based on the calculated 24-hour rolling averages.

Reflecting on the in situ PM_{2.5} AQ campaign and its progress so far, important points, lessons learned and challenges are summarized below:

- The installation of sensors in municipal buildings that have enough visitors instead of individual citizens is a direction decided by DAEM as a pilot leader following the findings of a previous citizen science European project COMPAIR. In this project that concluded in 2024, citizens were engaged to measure the air quality by installing devices at their households. The interest in volunteer participation was high; however, it was noticed that the collection of data was not continuous, individual communication with each end-user was rather difficult and in total the data collected was scarce.
- Currently, the Athens air quality campaign has had one interruption because one sensor went missing from its installation site. From the beginning, it was understood that, although uncommon, some sensors installed outdoors at public buildings could occasionally be lost or removed.
- Another general observation on the implementation of citizen science campaigns is that the time required to complete the campaign is related to many factors, especially in large metropolitan areas. More specifically, the installation of sensors is directly related to their technical requirements. In this campaign the PurpleAir devices required a plug for electricity outside of the building that is not frequent in Greece. Hence, additional work was required by an electrician to create the plug or to create a passage to an inside plug. This work is rather time-consuming taking also in account the bureaucratic procedures of a large municipality with many other needs and a lack of time and personnel to allocate for this work (it was mandatory that in municipal building

the procedure would be carried out by a certified electrician employed by the municipality). Also, the campaign foresees the installation in green areas, hence parks, where electricity installation is rather difficult to have as well as Wi-Fi connection.

- The onsite visits and audits necessary for the preparation of the campaign as well as for troubleshooting and error fixing are again time-consuming and require strong collaboration among DAEM and NOA.

Figure 14. NT location of 5th Municipal District at the Municipal Medical Center.

Indicative results from the UFP and BC mobile campaigns

The mobile campaigns covered three consecutive weeks of daily measurements. Measurements were performed (mid-June to mid-July 2025) in the morning and evening across the two routes in the centre of Athens. Over 20 people were invited, with 12 volunteers ultimately participating, selected from NOA personnel. The routes were specifically designed taking also into account Strava data (mapping along some of the most-travelled segments for pedestrians and runners in the centre of Athens, as reported in the Strava app database). The lengths of routes were 4.3-.4.4 km, with almost equal distance of T, UB and UG segments. A high route completion percentage (80/84, 95%) was achieved despite challenging summer conditions, including an extreme heatwave, when parks were closed on some days, due to fire hazard alerts. Along with UFP-BC monitors, EcoPulse TRH sensors were carried, reporting data at approximately 1/3 of the routes.

The main results from the pedestrian campaign for BC-UFPs mapping show that the concentrations were higher in the morning, especially during rush hours and during weekdays (Monday - Friday). Also, it was evident that in the National Garden (second route) the levels

of pollutants were lower than the Field of Mars. Moreover, the analysis on the 3 segments of each route appears to have interesting results for both pollutants. As illustrated in Figure 15, BC seems to have an increasing trend as we move from the urban green to the urban background and finally to the traffic areas. The same pattern was also seen for UFP number concentrations, and for LDSA. On the other hand, the diameter of the particles appears a decreasing rate, as expected, with the largest particles seen in the urban green spaces, and the smaller ultrafine particles emitted close to the traffic source.

Figure 15. (a) BC concentration, (b) UFP number concentration, (c) LDSA and (d) particle diameter, averaged for the 3 segments of the two routes. In green bars are presented the urban green spaces, in orange the urban background and in grey the traffic areas.

1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The AQ campaign has provided valuable input for the city and its yearly collected data so far and analysis by NOA, result to detailed outputs for the cities areas that suffer more from air pollution. The general outcome of the campaign in terms of policy making is profoundly the need for additional green spaces, the effective maintenance and enhancement of the existing green facilities e.g. on street trees, parks etc. This aligns with the city's actions on increasing the green infrastructure by planting more trees at annual basis², for example in since the beginning of 2025 more than 8000 new trees have been planted. Also, the results of the AQ campaign that was launched earlier than the Tree campaign, validate the scope of correlating the results of the two campaigns in order to extract policy recommendations on the reduction of air pollution at neighbourhood level. Hence, the Trees campaign will be complementary to the AQ as the existing trees of Athens are updated and mapped in a valuable trees repository to be used by the city while also trees' information is openly available for citizens to review

² <https://athenstreets.cityofathens.gr/>

such as each tree's environmental value and impact on the reduction air pollution, specific characteristics etc.

Following up on the AQ results so far, the planning of the Trees campaign was enhanced as the first area that will participate in the activities will be Kypseli, and then Gazi was decided to be the second area after an internal elaboration with the pilot team and the city. Both areas are expected to host a set of activities as also in Gazi one of the AQ sensors is installed in the 7th Municipal Medical Center, where the employees and the visitors have expressed high interest in the effect of the measured air pollution to public health.

Finally, the city has foreseen actions on tackling air pollution as this direction is clearly stated in the Net Zero Cities plan of Athens³. In more details, the plan is developing a prototype implementation for Athens in the area of Kypseli where the Athens Superblock project was launched in 2024 and will have 2 years duration. The project for Athens is referred as ASCEND, as an abbreviation of "Athens Superblock for Community Engagement and Neighbourhood Development", and is centred around an Elementary School of Athens. The measures of the Superblock are co-designed with the school community and include major interventions in the transport such as the promotion of mobility and accessibility for pedestrians and cyclists, the reduction or even elimination of vehicles' traffic in the area, the enhancement of the infrastructure by pavements repairment and addition of green locations where possible.

³ <https://netzerocities.eu/athens-pilot-activity-ascend/>

2 Urban Trees Campaign

The Trees campaign focuses on citizen observations to find out more about city trees, their key characteristics and state. The aim of the campaign is to engage volunteer citizens and communities in Athens to help improve urban greenspace monitoring and planning. The Trees campaign is designed and prepared in strong collaboration with the Greening Department of the Municipality of Athens and CIBOS. Personnel from the Greening Department is engaged in the project since the launch of Urban ReLeaf, aiming to exploit the valuable results of the campaign to create an up-to-date Tree Registry for Athens and management tool for the city.

2.1 Context and Objectives

One of the major challenges of the city of Athens is the lack of greenspaces. Speaking with numbers, the Municipality of Athens manages 1.346 greenspaces, covering a total area of 3.942 acres, of which 3.347 acres are pure greenspaces (Figure 16). The updated Climate Change Adaptation Plan on Resilience and Sustainability⁴ includes activities to reduce the emissions and promote initiatives against the impacts of climate change. The Action Plan of the city highlights the trees management and mapping in the Pillar A.1 of Open Data and specifically in A1.5 for Tree Identity. It is mentioned that the City of Athens owns over 120.000 trees which are growing within the city boundaries. The need for a registry for these trees is stated, focusing on an application that will update all of the tree characteristics such as their position, type, occupancy, age, classification, and canopy. This objective is tackled through Urban ReLeaf.

Additionally, one of the aims of the current mayorship is to increase the amount of greenery per inhabitant through regeneration and the creation of new greenspaces and to plant 5.000 new trees every year. So far, approximately 7.500 new trees have been planted. Also, the main issue that the Trees campaign will tackle is the lack of the tree registry for the City of Athens and the update of the information of each tree.

Taking this into consideration, DAEM, through Urban ReLeaf project designs the campaign of updating the existing trees of Athens by a mobile application developed by CIBOS, the tree registry app.

The main goal is to involve citizens in mapping the trees along the streets of Athens to create a shared tree registry. This will help improve the management and maintenance of green spaces in the city, as there is currently no digital tool that accurately records the location, condition, size, or other characteristics of Athens' trees. There is ongoing research at the Agriculture University of Athens on the creation of a trees dataset, however this database is not openly accessible and with the minimum information. The Trees campaign aims to update this information and add more valuable details for each tree. This database was provided by the city to CIBOS and integrated in the Application. Then, the citizens will edit each entry and provide more details.

⁴ https://resilientcitiesnetwork.org/downloadable_resources/Network/Athens-Resilience-Strategy-English.pdf

Figure 16. Greenspaces in Athens.

In parallel, a strong collaboration of DAEM for the campaign and the Tree Registry is a municipal employee Ms. Magdalini Dapsopoulou⁵ that is a forester in the Department of Greenery & Urban Fauna and a PhD candidate in the Agricultural University of Athens. Ms. Dapsopoulou has proposed advanced functionality be developed and integrated into the Tree App, based on her research activities. The objective is to evaluate and monitor aboveground biomass, carbon storage, and CO₂ sequestration by urban trees. Namely, a statistically sound allometric equation is integrated in the App for estimating the total dry biomass of urban trees, based on two key dendrometric variables: diameter at breast height and tree height. This equation provides automated estimates for: total dry biomass, stored carbon and CO₂ sequestration for each tree that is mapped or updated within the App.

The integration of this equation transforms the Tree App into a scientifically grounded tool for the quantification of ecosystem services provided by urban vegetation, enhancing:

- Evidence-based decision-making in tree management and planting strategies,
- Dynamic carbon balance monitoring at the municipal or neighbourhood scale,
- Citizen and stakeholder engagement through access to high-accuracy environmental data.

The utilization of this scientific model and its integration into digital tools directly supports the objectives of Urban ReLeaf, promotes transparency, sustainable urban governance, and the resilience of cities in the face of the climate crisis.

2.2 Design and Implementation

During the first year of the project in June 2024, a co-creation workshop was organised where various stakeholders and citizens groups were invited. In a session dedicated to the tree registry, municipal employees from the Greening Department, the National Garden Agency

⁵ Dapsopoulou, M., & Zianis, D. (2025). Biomass Allometries for Urban Trees: A Case Study in Athens, Greece. *Forests*, 16(3), 466. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f16030466>

and other group citizens participated in order to identify the city needs regarding greenspaces, tree registration and improvement of environmental conditions.

Moreover, several meetings followed with the administrative personnel of the Greening Department to identify the features of the tree registry application based on the city's needs and how this application could support and improve their workload. Based on these meetings and focus groups, the process of the tree campaigns is designed. The initial point is to develop a comprehensive data platform for Athens including a tool to register and monitor tree-related tasks to improve the transparency and the capacity for maintenance and the whole plan for activities on urban green space.

The Greening Department provided all the registered trees per municipal district to be integrated into the application aiming at enhancing the tree registry of the city so far and at mapping the new ones. In the next section, a detailed campaign plan will be presented.

In consultation with NOA a comprehensive categorization was conducted for all tree species within the Athens registry, distinguishing them as native, alien, or invasive alien. This information is valuable for the creation of an integrated tree registry, a tool designed to advance strategic urban green management and promote biodiversity. Beyond fulfilling a key project KPI (the identification of over 500 invasive alien specimens), mapping the distribution and composition of these invasive species is essential for mitigating their impact. This, in turn, facilitates the implementation of precise, site-specific control measures by the Greening Department.

After the launch of the initial version of the app, preparatory activities and internal testing session in DAEM was organised for adjustments and updates as well as the integration of the current city tree registry is completed. Afterwards, a wide testing session was held in the Greening department in April 2025 with the participation of municipal gardeners, employees and administration and valuable feedback was collected (Figure 17). This was gathered by CIBOS to further improve the app and prepare a new version.

Figure 17. Testing the tree registry app with the Municipality of Athens.

As mentioned above, a series of preparatory actions have taken place in order to finalize the application and launch the campaigns. Hence, the campaign is planned to be launched in the last semester of 2025 and includes various actions to be taken such as the engagement of school communities to mapping of the trees, pop-up events, engagement initiatives in environmental events, publicity of the campaign and calls for action for the citizens through social media and other municipal channels e.g. advertisements in the Municipal Radio etc. Specifically, for the Trees campaign in schools the ethics forms have been prepared and refer to the informed consent of the school administration and the parent or legal guardian of the students to participate. Also, a demographics questionnaire template is prepared. The templates are included in [Appendix C](#) in English and in Greek. The templates were checked for legal compliance by DAEM's Legal Department and followed the approach of Urban ReLeaf on the engagement of youth audiences.

2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The Urban ReLeaf Athens Tree Registry platform is designed to support data collection and management across the entire Athens Municipality. However, the initial campaign will focus on the Kypseli neighbourhood, a densely populated area identified by the city as having limited green space. Starting in Kypseli, the initiative aims to address urgent urban greening needs while fostering community engagement in one of Athens's most vibrant yet underserved districts. A pop-up event will be organised inviting citizens to test the tree registry app. Then, the next actions are planned to be held by engaging school communities, equipping students in High and Junior High schools with mobile phones pre-installed with the mapping app. Students will take part in guided walks to map trees in their neighbourhoods, incorporating gamification elements to make the process interactive and educational.

In the Athens pilot, the full ecosystem of the Urban ReLeaf Tree Registry platform has been deployed, offering a comprehensive suite of tools designed to support collaborative urban tree mapping and management. This ecosystem consists of three interconnected components:

- **Urban ReLeaf Athens Tree Registry Application:** A user-friendly mobile application tailored for both citizens and expert users (Figure 18). It enables on-the-go tree documentation, allowing users to add new entries, enrich existing records, and upload geotagged photos.
- **Urban ReLeaf Athens Tree Registry Backend:** The central data infrastructure that powers the platform. It securely stores, processes, and synchronizes all tree-related data, ensuring consistency across devices and interfaces. The backend also supports authentication and authorization, data validation, and versioning.
- **Urban ReLeaf Athens Tree Registry Web Interface:** robust browser-based dashboard developed for expert users. It provides advanced tools for data visualization, filtering, editing, and analysis, enabling informed decision-making and strategic planning for urban greening initiatives.

Together, these components form a dynamic and scalable system that fosters community engagement, supports data-driven urban forestry, and strengthens collaboration between citizens and city departments.

The Urban ReLeaf Athens Tree Registry platform offers full multilingual support in both English and Greek, ensuring accessibility for a diverse range of users. This dual-language functionality allows citizens and experts to interact with the app, web interface, and backend tools in their preferred language, fostering inclusive participation and enhancing user experience across the local and international community.

Figure 18. Screenshots: Urban ReLeaf – Athens Tree Registry Application.

2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

The Urban ReLeaf Athens Tree Registry platform was launched using an initial dataset provided by the Athens Greening Department. However, this dataset was incomplete and outdated, highlighting the need for continuous updates and enrichment through active citizen participation.

The Urban ReLeaf application empowers residents to help document Athens's trees in ways that match their interests and availability. Contributions are flexible - users can add new trees with basic information or enrich existing entries with additional details. There's no obligation to complete every field; even a single photo or a few attributes make a meaningful impact. Someone might upload a photo without any accompanying data or choose to provide only a few attributes. By keeping participation open-ended and user-friendly, the app lowers barriers and encourages involvement from people of all backgrounds, regardless of expertise or time constraints. Citizens can contribute by adding or updating the fields listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Collected tree data fields.

Field Name	Description
Species	Selected from a list of species, e.g. Acacia, Spindle Tree, Boxelder Maple, Plane Tree, Scots pine, Rose of Sharon, Canary Island Date Palm, Jacaranda etc.
Status	Selected from a list of statuses: Good, Average, Poor, Dead, Tree is missing
Location	GIS location (latitude, longitude) and Address
Pictures	User must upload a main picture and a picture of the tree's trunk when adding a new tree. Picture of the tree's leaves and additional pictures may be uploaded.
Tree Height	The Height of the tree. Available Options: "0-1 m", "1-2 m", "2-4 m", "4-8 m", "8-16 m", "Above 16 m"
Trunk Inclination to the Ground	The angle of inclination of the Tree trunk in relation to the ground. Available Options: "0-8 cm", "8-16 cm", "16-24 cm", "24-32 cm", "32-40 cm", "40-48 cm", "48-56 cm", "Above 56 cm"
Stem Diameter	The Tree stem diameter at 1.5 meters from the ground. Available Options: "0-15 degrees", "15-30 degrees", "Above 30 degrees"

The Urban ReLeaf Athens tree registry application has been available on both the Play Store and the App Store, enabling citizens to easily install, register and begin contributing. Combined with the organisation of an event that involved the employees of the Greening Department, this accessibility has led to the collection of valuable data. A statistical overview of the data collected thus far can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Overview of Tree Registry Contributions to Date.

Users	
Total Citizen Registrations	25
Citizens registered in the last 30 days	1
Total Expert Users	5
Trees	
Total Trees	84278
Total Community Trees	27
Total City Trees added after app initialization	5
Community Trees added in the last 30 days	0
Tree Pictures	
Total tree pictures uploaded	96
Tree pictures uploaded in the last 30 days	0
Pictures uploaded during tree creation	96
Pictures added to existing trees	0
Community Updates (Suggestions)	
Number of Suggested Statuses added to trees	8
Number of Suggested Total Tree Field Values added to trees	18
Number of suggested "Tree Height" values added to trees	6
Number of suggested "Stem Circumference" values added to trees	6
Number of suggested "Shape of Planting Area" values added to trees	6
Number of trees per tree species	
Persian Silk Tree	1
Acacia	1
Jacaranda	1
Bay Laurel	2
Olive Tree	1
Judas Tree	1
Cypress	3
Silver Poplar	2
Mulberry	12
Plane Tree	2
Maple	4
Chinese Banyan	1
Carob Tree	1
Number of trees per district	
3η Municipal District	10
7η Municipal District	22

2.5 Findings and Reflections

Since the campaign has not yet been officially launched, findings and results will be collected, analysed, and reported in a future deliverable. In addition, lessons learned and best practices from the campaign implementation will be documented after the activities are completed.

2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

As noted in Section 2.5 above, the recommendations and future steps will be presented in a future deliverable after the campaign has been completed.

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3 Heat Stress Campaign

The last campaign focuses on acquiring volunteer-based observations to address urgent climate issues related to heat stress discomfort. The purpose of the data collection is to help improve urban greenspace planning. The TRH campaign was the first to be launched and completed by the Athens pilot, since it was planned to be executed during the summer period in Athens when temperatures are remarkably increased. The preparation foresaw the onboarding of population that is walking within Athens and was initially designed for one of the seven municipal districts of Athens. However, the close liaison with the Department of Cleaning expanded the data collection to end-users in the whole area of Athens and in all the seven districts. Also, it was of great importance for the city since it provides a basis for further correlation of data with other environmental aspects such as the trees' coverage and green areas. Finally, the recent years heatwaves are not extreme environmental incidents happening scarcely in Athens, rather than a normality for the city ecosystem during the summer period.

3.1 Context and Objectives

The City of Athens has identified the challenges and focused in recent years on the creation of a greener city enhancing the indicator of quality of life as a crucial urban target. Since Athens is a city that suffers from heatwaves and poor air quality⁶, the need for a cultural change to understand, support, and promote its green infrastructures is primordial. To this dimension, Athens has launched its Resilience Strategy that maps the city's needs and suggests a set of practicable actions for the implementation towards an open, proactive and green city. The Strategy includes a Climate Change Adaptation Plan on Resilience and Sustainability that focuses on reducing air-pollution and identifying measures for resilient climate transformations. More specifically, the Plan for Athens provisions measure under the pillar of crisis preparedness and management for the protection of population against heatwaves, especially for population that is vulnerable or is exposed in extreme conditions

Finally, citizen engagement in measuring heat exposure is a top priority in order to observe and monitor urban areas, support informed decision-making, and help the city meet its commitment to reduce emissions by 2030 and transition toward climate neutrality.

3.2 Design and Implementation

The implementation and execution of this campaign was launched with the co-creation workshop's organisation in June 2024 with a dedicated session on heat stress and climate adaptation plans targeting groups of citizens affected by climate conditions, such as seniors and children, as well as municipal employees working outdoors.

The outcome of this co-creation event was the design of this specific campaign focusing on the wellbeing and the improvement of quality of life by tackling the challenge of heat stress. During the first year of Urban ReLeaf project, the campaign was designed by DAEM and ICSS teams; more specifically meetings with stakeholders, Municipality of Athens and sensors development were held.

During the preparatory activities with the Municipality of Athens, as the main enlisted stakeholder, the respective department to be involved was the Agency of Cleaning and Recycling and more specifically the cleaning workers on the streets. This group of employees is exposed to extreme temperature conditions since they work outdoors. It is decided to

⁶ Mavrakis, A., Kapsali, A., Tsiros, I.X. et al. Air quality and meteorological patterns of an early spring heatwave event in an industrialized area of Attica, Greece. *Euro-Mediterr J Environ Integr* 6, 25 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41207-020-00237-0>

distribute portable sensors measuring temperature and relative humidity. In the next section, a detailed description of the sensors and the technology used is presented. Hence, in June 2025, sensors were distributed by DAEM to 92 volunteers in all 7 districts of Athens, used until the end of September 2025. The aim of the campaign that was 4 months of heat discomfort, temperature and humidity data collection is succeeded. Currently the progress focuses on the conclusion of the campaign, by organising closure events for the retrieval of the sensors by the municipal workers and the presentation of preliminary results to them. Finally, ICCS will undertake the overall data analysis and outcomes.

3.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The city of Athens is divided into 7 districts. They are under the Decentralization and Administration Agency of the Municipality, responsible for the supervision and coordination of municipal communities, acting at the same time as Citizens' Service Centers. Each Municipal District has subdepartments of the Greening Department, Cleaning Department etc. DAEM had a face-to-face meeting with the Deputy Mayor of Waste Management and the Head of the sector and organised the campaign of TRH sensors distribution to the cleaning workers in all the 7 districts. With this process, data collection from all the Athens area is completed.

Two events followed the above-mentioned meeting, where the cleaning workers were informed about the project, the scope of the campaign and a group of them expressed their intension to participate volunteering. Then, DAEM team organised events in each district distributing the respective sensors to the end-users, all completed by the end of June 2025.

The wearable sensors (**Error! Reference source not found.**) provided to participants are designed to capture both environmental conditions and personal perceptions in real time. They record location data (latitude and longitude), temperature (°C), and relative humidity (%) every 30 seconds when movement is detected. Alongside these measurements, participants can also report their own thermal experience and perception, helping to link objective environmental data with subjective comfort levels. The main features and functions of the sensors are outlined below:

- **Motion and Step detection**
 - Allow to collect observations only when the citizen is walking.
 - The sensor should not be used during cycling or when the citizen is on car, bus
- **Data collection**
 - Every 30 seconds when movement is detected based on the latitude and longitude changes.
- **Inclusive design**
 - Standalone sensor with LoRa transmission
 - BLE sensors operating in conjunction with the EcoPulse mobile application
- **Rechargeable**
 - Rechargeable battery
 - Type-C socket
 - Separate Charging LED
- **Status button + LED**
 - LED: Sensor Activation, Pairing, Deactivation, Factory reset, Low battery, Error, Thermal discomfort
 - Button: De-(Activation), Factory reset, Thermal discomfort
- **Smart openings** that enable the intake of outside air to assess ambient air conditions.
- **QR code**
 - For pairing the BLE sensor with the user's mobile phone and the EcoPulse mobile application.

Figure 19: TRH Sensor

The TRH measurements are either transmitted to the EcoPulse mobile application via Bluetooth, or via LoRaWAN gateways back to the data storage server. For the Athens pilot mainly the LoRa sensors were exploited since municipal cleaning workers cannot use their mobile while working.

3.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

The engagement process for this group of end users involved a series of meetings with the City's Cleaning and Recycling Agency to recruit cleaning workers. This was followed by meetings with the Head of the Cleaning Department and then separate meetings with the responsible administrative staff of each of the seven districts to distribute sensors to a total of 92 municipal employee volunteers. During these meetings, employees were informed about the project's objectives and the pilot implementation. They expressed strong interest in participating, as their work exposes them to extreme climate conditions that can affect their health. As a result, they are particularly motivated to take part in initiatives of this kind.

Participation was voluntary and anonymized. The key data collected included the location of the end user, temperature and relative humidity, and the level of thermal discomfort experienced by the user. To this end, a respective consent form is prepared and signed by each participant. This ethics form prior to the distribution was checked for legal compliance by the Legal Department of DAEM and the respective Legal Department of the Municipality. Also, for the engagement of the end-users an anonymized demographic questionnaire was shared with the participants. Both the templates for consent forms and the demographics questionnaire are included in English and Greek in [Appendix B](#).

The majority of campaign end users are women, accounting for 66% of participants. The largest age group is 45–54 years old, followed by those aged 55–64, indicating that the audience is predominantly middle-aged. In terms of education, most respondents have

completed secondary education only, with far fewer holding tertiary degrees. This suggests that the campaign primarily reached individuals with basic formal education, placing the end-user group largely within a lower socioeconomic profile.

Data were collected over a four-month period, from June 1st to September 30th, 2025. During this time, a total of 157451 data points were recorded – including 78.681 temperature readings, 78.681 relative humidity reading, 87 reports of thermal discomfort, and 2 instances identified as cool spots. Visualization of TRH and thermal discomfort data are depicted in EcoPulse Web Platform developed by ICSS team (Figure 20). The EcoPulse platform is publicly available and freely accessible.

Figure 20. EcoPulse Web App - Visualization of temperature data for Athens from June 1st to September 30th.

Data will be presented to the end-users as well as to city officials and the mayor's office since they have expressed interest. Moreover, since climate mitigation is one of the strategic plans of Athens, data and outputs of this specific campaign are related to other initiatives in the same field.

3.5 Findings and Reflections

Participation & Data Coverage

The Athens campaign achieved strong device deployment and data return rates. Of the 92 devices distributed, 84 successfully recorded and transmitted data to the servers — a 91% return rate. These devices collected 157451 observations in total, of which 142774 were recorded within 50km of the city centre (Figure 21 shows the spatial coverage of these observations). Data collection was sustained over 4 months, with 90 out of 122 days between June and September recording at least one measurement. June and August achieved full temporal coverage with at least 22 observations recorded every day. On average, each device recorded 856 observations, though this varied considerably between devices. Figure 22 shows the amount of data collected by each device, ranked from highest to lowest. Following a pattern observed in other cities, data collection showed significant participation inequality: 70% of all observations came from just 20% of the devices.

Figure 21. Spatial coverage of sensor measurements in Athens on a log scale.

Figure 22: Amount of data by device. (Counting a pair of relative humidity and temperature as one observation and ignoring the button records).

A distinguishing feature of the Athens campaign's data was the timing of the observations. 70% of observations were recorded between 04:00 and 12:00 unlike the other large campaigns in Riga and Utrecht, where most of the measurements occurred in the late afternoon and evenings.

This difference reflects the difference in participant groups: whereas other cities relied on interested citizens collecting data during their free time or commutes, Athens' participants were street cleaning workers gathering data during their morning work shifts.

Figure 23 displays all temperature measurements collected in summer, overlaid over the same 24-hour cycle. The data reveals warming through the morning hours as expected. Other expected features like a peak around 12 followed by gradual cooling is not as well pronounced due to much sparser data. This morning-focused data collection provides insights during a period underrepresented in the other cities' campaigns. The plot also highlights the temperature ranges measured during each hour, demonstrating the diversity of microclimatic conditions experienced across the city and hints at autocorrelation from trips represented by the 'streaks' of points in the cloud.

Figure 23. All temperature measurements throughout the days, with the median line and the 25 and 75 quartiles for each hour shown.

Temperature Findings

Using data collected during the morning work period (04:00 to 12:00) reveals only moderate temperature increases as the day progresses. The median temperature across all observations rises from 29.2°C to 32.7°C over this eight-hour window, which is uncharacteristically flat due to high temperatures observed during hour 4. The median

reference temperature for comparison is only 23.1°C and noon has the same temperature as the mobile sensors. This early in the morning are usually the coolest temperatures in a city.

However, these aggregate statistics mask heat exposures experienced by individual workers. During the peak summer months of July and August (62 days total), 58 days saw at least one worker experience temperature increases of 5°C or more during their morning shift. Every day got at least as hot as 30°C, and on 48 out of 62 days, at least one worker measured 35°C or more.

To contextualize these mobile measurements, we compared them with data from nearby meteorological stations, which record temperature at 2m height in highly controlled environments with proper radiation shielding. On average, the low-cost sensors measured 3.76°C higher than the reference station temperature for the same time and day. This systematic difference reflects both the genuine microclimatic variability experienced at street level and potential measurement biases inherent in the mobile sensor design, particularly solar heating of the sensor casing.

Data Quality & Challenges

While the Athens campaign successfully collected a substantial dataset capturing heat exposure among outdoor workers, the data presents several quality challenges common to mobile, low-cost sensor deployments. These challenges stem from GPS accuracy issues, lack of radiation shielding, lack of consistent handling of the sensors and the inherently unstructured nature of opportunistic data collection.

GPS Positioning Issues

GPS accuracy proved inconsistent across the dataset. We observe seemingly random movements with rapid position changes that are physically impossible for pedestrian movement. These patterns likely result from poor satellite reception in urban canyons or signal interference. This is then often followed by large jumps presumably as the GPS updates and gets closer to the real position. Figure 24 shows such a pattern that is very common. It is in fact so common that in Athens, for each day a device recorded data, at least one observation exceeded speeds of 20km/h, while the median walking speed is only 1.35 km/h. This median speed is lower than in other cities, but expected due to the users doing work rather than commuting or leisure walking. This is further reflected in the spatial movement patterns, which show more backtracking, lingering at specific locations, and repeated street-side switching—characteristic of street cleaning work rather than the more linear paths typical of commuting or leisure walking observed in other cities.

Crucially these are just theories. Without a second control instrument it is impossible to be certain if and how these adjustment processes happen. Unfortunately, these patterns only sometimes correlate with the GPS accuracy scores provided by the sensors as there are many disturbances that are not covered by these scores.

These erroneous locations must be identified and then discarded or corrected for spatial analyses. They represent a non-trivial portion of the dataset. We developed methods to classify bad GPS based on movement patterns. Currently these indicate that about one half of the observations need to be discarded (or in some way corrected).

Temperature Measurement Limitations

Unlike meteorological stations with standardized radiation shielding, the mobile sensors' temperature readings are susceptible to solar heating effects. When exposed to direct sunlight, the sensor casings heat up, causing measurements to reflect device temperature rather than true air temperature. The positioning of the sensor relative to the sun, for instance, whether worn on a belt facing the sun or shielded by a backpack, can introduce measurement variations of several degrees Celsius, compounding with the amount of exposure. These factors create unobserved measurement errors that vary with sun position, cloud cover and other shadings and sensor placement on the user. While we can control for some factors (cloud cover data, 3D models for shading), the users introduce many unobserved disturbances.

The 3.76°C average difference compared to meteorological stations likely reflects both genuine street-level heat (from radiation, limited airflow, and surface heating) and systematic measurement bias from inadequate radiation protection. Disentangling these components requires either better radiation shielding (bigger and more expensive) in future deployments or controlled testing of the devices under various conditions to develop correction factors. Another approach to improve data quality relies more on the citizens, by building resources for the users to flag or adjust faulty data in hindsight or in the moment. If different sensor handling improves data quality, then future campaigns could also benefit from participant instructions on optimal sensor placement to minimize solar heating effects and or finding behaviour protocols for better GPS tracking. Good instructions would need to be found, written and tested first.

Methodological Considerations

The unstructured, opportunistic nature of mobile sensor data contrasts with traditional urban temperature studies, which typically employ fixed transects traversed at predetermined times or work with stationary sensors or existing sensors. This applies mostly for the 3 larger campaigns in Athens, Riga and Utrecht.

These data require sophisticated modelling techniques to enable meaningful comparisons between semi-random paths recorded at different times of day, on different days, with sometimes uncertain locations, and under variable external conditions. Despite these challenges, the dataset remains valuable. With thorough cleaning and careful selection, these observations can still describe the thermal landscape of Athens and reveal patterns of heat exposure among outdoor workers—insights that would be difficult to obtain through traditional methods.

Next Steps

The data if correctly treated could be used to develop and train microclimate models, or to validate existing ones. The data could also be used as a covariate in other studies. For instance, heat-inequality or topics more specific to the work environment.

3.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The Heat Stress campaign was the first that has been launched and completed by the Athens pilot. It was executed during the summer period 2025 when temperatures were increased. The campaign is considered as successful, since data collection is completed for the whole city, namely it covered areas from the 7 Municipal Districts, that Athens is divided. The active participation of a quite great number volunteers cleaning workers conducted to valuable outputs. Out of 92 participants, only 1 participant dropped out and in summary, as already mentioned, of the total of 92 devices distributed, 84 successfully recorded and transmitted data to the servers, that means a 91% return rate.

The results, depicted in the previous section, were presented in the Cleaning Department by the end of the campaign, and they will be combined with the city policies already being in place. In more detail, they will be correlated with the Climate adaptation plan. The city's climate adaptation plan is expanded to include more objectives for example: The reduction of high temperatures in the city and the urban heat island effect, protection of public health and support to vulnerable populations, improving of air quality, data-based decision making and policies, informing, educating and raising citizens' awareness of climate change etc. This action plan includes policies, recommendations and actions for citizens and it will include also initiatives for the cleaning street workers that are affected by the climate conditions.

Diverse initiatives and other relevant activities are already planned for the city to tackle the climate challenges and improve the conditions of everyday life both of citizens and city employees. Indicatively mentioned, planning for the creation of cooling and protection stations ensuring high-impact placement in heat-exposed zones, equipped with shade-providing greenery and evaporative surfaces, including misting systems and water stations for hydration and immediate relief. These cooling stations/benches are suggested by the city to be installed in specific locations that heat exposure is higher and lack of shadow and greening spaces is evident. Further actions will include the promotion of routes for city employees that will include these cooling stations as proposed places for a break during working hours especially in the summer.

Finally, regarding the thermal discomfort the TRH volunteers pressed the sensor button only 87 times during the pilot implementation, while the highest temperatures were measured during 25th July 2025. This specific day the forecasted heatwave resulted to an official regulation of the Cleaning Department to assume any working activity by 11.30 in the morning. Hence, the approach and policies of the city departments have been validated by the TRH campaign. Also, regarding the number of thermal discomfort observations, it was elaborated with the end-users and there is an outcome that this metric is also relevant to the daily exposure of each individual in heat as this can result to higher resistance in heat. Also, thermal discomfort was identified as a metric that is depending on many factors such as the general health of the individual, age and other characteristics, hydration level, temperature received by reflecting surfaces, clothing, duration of exposure etc.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Appendices

Appendix A

Template of the Site Characterization Form for the air quality campaign.

Identification:		
Site code		
Pod Number		
City		
Site address (street + street number)		
Postal code		
Contact Person		
Other Characteristics of site		
Location:		
Site type		
Building type		
GPS Coordinates		
Altitude (m asl)		
Traffic impacts:		
Date		
Starting time of count		
Nearest Road <i>Mesogeion Ave. , two way, three lanes per way + one lane byway, Primary OSM type</i>	Light vehicles	
	Heavy vehicles	
	Mopeds	
	Buses	
Traffic Characteristics:		
Traffic volume within 50m of the site (>10000 mvh/day)		
Distance to nearest street		
Total width of the street (m)		
Distance to nearby "influential" street		
Distance to nearest intersection (>25m)		
Distance to nearest traffic light (>25m)		
Distance to nearest bus-stop (>25m)		
Buildings:		
Sampling height above street level		
Average height of buildings on sampling side of street (m)		
Average height of buildings on opposite side of street (m)		
Other impacts within 100 meters:		
Large/medium point sources. Describe		
Small industries. Describe		
Parking lot (50 or more spaces)		
Warehouse		
Construction activity		
Other (e.g. restaurant, grill house/bakery)		
On site Utilities:		
Outdoor socket for AC		
Possible connection to an indoor socket		
AC line stability		

Uninterrupted AC line	
Required electrical equipment	
Wi-Fi availability. Indicate distance of the device from the receiver	
Wi-Fi signal strength.	
Wi-Fi SSID / Password	
Installation:	
Existing infrastructure	
Possibility to drill holes	
Required hardware	
Required equipment	
Safe to install, access and handle	
Micro-siting:	
Inlet height above surface (>1.5m)	
Distance of applied sampler to vertical surfaces (> 0.5m)	
Unrestricted flow (arc of 270°)	
Distance from exhaust airways and AC units (< 3m)	
Distance from chimneys and kitchen exhausts (>5m)	
Distance from trees/foliage (> tree height)	
Smoking area	
Children's gathering spot	
Protected space or exposed to the elements (rain, frost, snow)	
Dusty/unclean environment	
Accessibility:	
Working days and hours	
Non-working hours during weekdays	
Weekends	
Secure during off hours	
Guard	
Video surveillance	
Visible from street	
Required permissions	

(provide satellite imagery and on-site photos)

- i) Aerial View, far (sat, e.g. Google Earth)
 -
- ii) Aerial view, close (sat, e.g. Google Earth)
 -
- iii) Indicative photos showing the exact location from various directions
 -
- iv) Indicative photos showing the surroundings from the the viewpoint of the exact location
 -

Appendix B

Template of the informed consent for the TRH campaign in English and in Greek, also of the demographic anonymized questionnaire.

Consent Form

During June – September 2025 a citizen science campaign will take place under the European research project Urban ReLeaf. In the campaign, volunteer citizens will collect environmental data and observations using new technologies.

Specifically, the citizens will receive a sensor that collects data on the temperature and relevant humidity, while also they have a button to declare thermal discomfort. Citizens will carry the sensor while walking in the city for the above mentioned time frame and after the end of the campaign the sensors will be returned.

For research purposes, we would also like to collect socio-demographic information that is: gender, age, and parental education level.

Participation is voluntary and you are free to withdraw your participation at any time.

Below you will find more information about the study and how it will be organised.

Information about the Urban ReLeaf project

Urban ReLeaf (urbanreleaf.eu) is a European project. The project invites citizens to collect environmental observations using new technologies. Together, we develop innovations and new greening policies to fight climate change. Our vision is an inclusive and green transition.

The project is coordinated by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Austria.

In Athens, the project activities will be led and implemented by DAEM. For further information, you can contact: Dimitra Tsakanika, d.tsakanika@daem.gr and Iliia Christantoni, i.christantoni@daem.gr.

Information about the campaign

DAEM will organize the campaign during June – September 2025. During this activity, volunteer citizens will receive a sensor that collects data on the temperature and relevant humidity in each location, while also they have a button to declare thermal discomfort. Citizens will carry the sensor while walking in the city for the above mentioned time frame and after the end of the campaign the sensors will be returned.

Privacy and confidentiality

The data collected through the technologies during the Urban ReLeaf activities are controlled by I-Sense Research Group, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), NTUA, Athens, Greece.

Urban ReLeaf has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No.101086638. UK participants in the Urban ReLeaf project are supported by United Kingdom Research and Innovation ("UKRI") Innovate UK under grant agreements 10061290 and 10041792.

The handling of the personal data provided, including anonymization and sharing of anonymized data, with scientific project partners of the Urban ReLeaf for analysis, is managed by DAEM.

The data will be kept confidential and will be anonymized for scientific purposes, such as to analyze the participants of the Urban ReLeaf project. This data collection is necessary for the scientific purposes of the Urban ReLeaf project and complies with the requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Consent

Please give your consent by marking the phrases with an 'X':

- I have read and understood the details of the Urban ReLeaf study and I agree to participate in the study. I acknowledge the terms and conditions outlined in this consent form.
- I consent to the publication of the research results. My name will not be published at any stage of research.

Name:

Date:

Signature:

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Gender:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other
- I prefer not to answer

Age group:

- Under 18 years old
- 19-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65-74 years old
- Over 75 years old
- I prefer not to answer

Level of education:

- Secondary education
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other degree
- No education
- I prefer not to answer

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Έντυπο Συναίνεσης

Κατά το χρονικό διάστημα Ιούνιος - Σεπτέμβριος 2025 θα λάβει χώρα μια καμπάνια επιστήμης πολιτών (citizen science) του Ευρωπαϊκού ερευνητικού έργου Urban ReLeaf. Κατά τη διάρκεια της καμπάνιας/δράσης εθελοντές πολίτες θα συλλέξουν περιβαλλοντικά δεδομένα και παρατηρήσεις με τη χρήση νέων τεχνολογιών.

Πιο συγκεκριμένα θα διαμοιραστούν σε πολίτες αισθητήρες που μετρούν την θερμοκρασία και τη σχετική υγρασία ενώ παράλληλα διαθέτουν ένα κουμπί με το οποίο οι πολίτες μπορούν να δηλώσουν την δυσφορία τους από την υψηλή θερμοκρασία. Οι πολίτες θα έχουν μαζί τους τον αισθητήρα για όσες ώρες κινούνται στην πόλη περπατώντας κατά το παραπάνω χρονικό διάστημα και στο τέλος της καμπάνιας θα τον επιστρέψουν.

Επιπλέον, για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς θα συλλεχθούν δημογραφικά δεδομένα εφόσον επιθυμούν να απαντήσουν: φύλο, ηλικία και επίπεδο εκπαίδευσης.

Η συμμετοχή είναι εθελοντική και είστε ελεύθεροι να διακόψετε τη συμμετοχή σας ανά πάσα στιγμή.

Παρακάτω παραθέτονται περισσότερες πληροφορίες για την καμπάνια και τη διοργάνωση.

Πληροφορίες για το έργο

Το Urban ReLeaf (urbanreleaf.eu) είναι ένα Ευρωπαϊκό ερευνητικό έργο που προσκαλεί πολίτες να συλλέξουν περιβαλλοντικά δεδομένα και παρατηρήσεις μέσω νέων τεχνολογιών. Στόχος είναι να αναπτυχθούν καινοτόμες δράσεις που θα οδηγήσουν σε νέες πολιτικές για το περιβάλλον ώστε να αντιμετωπιστεί η κλιματική αλλαγή και να επιτευχθεί μια συμπεριληπτική πράσινη μετάβαση

Το έργο συντονίζει το International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Αυστρία.

Στην Αθήνα η πιλοτική εφαρμογή και οι σχετικές δράσεις συντονίζονται από τη ΔΑΕΜ. Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με: Δήμητρα Τσακανικά, d.tsakanika@daem.gr και Ίλια Χρισταντώνη, i.christantoni@daem.gr.

Πληροφορίες για την καμπάνια

Η ΔΑΕΜ θα οργανώσει την δράση κατά το χρονικό διάστημα Ιούνιος - Σεπτέμβριος 2025. Θα διαμοιραστούν σε πολίτες αισθητήρες που μετρούν την θερμοκρασία και τη σχετική υγρασία σε κάθε τοποθεσία ενώ παράλληλα διαθέτουν ένα κουμπί με το οποίο οι πολίτες μπορούν να δηλώσουν την δυσφορία τους από την υψηλή θερμοκρασία. Οι πολίτες θα έχουν μαζί τους τον αισθητήρα για όσες ώρες κινούνται στην πόλη περπατώντας κατά το παραπάνω χρονικό διάστημα και στο τέλος της καμπάνιας θα το επιστρέψουν.

Urban ReLeaf has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No.101086638. UK participants in the Urban ReLeaf project are supported by United Kingdom Research and Innovation ("UKRI") Innovate UK under grant agreements 10061290 and 10041792.

Ιδιωτικότητα και εμπιστευτικότητα

Τα δεδομένα που συλλέγονται μέσω των αισθητήρων κατά τη διάρκεια των δράσεων ελέγχονται από την ερευνητική ομάδα i-Sense, Ερευνητικό Πανεπιστημιακό Ινστιτούτο Συστημάτων Επικοινωνιών και Υπολογιστών (ΕΠΙΣΕΥ), Εθνικό Μετσόβειο Πολυτεχνείο, Αθήνα, Ελλάδα.

Για τη διαχείριση των προσωπικών δεδομένων, της ανωνυμοποίησής τους και του διαμοιρασμού μόνο ανωνυμοποιημένων δεδομένων με τους εταίρους του έργου, υπεύθυνα είναι η ΔΑΕΜ.

Τα δεδομένα θα παραμείνουν εμπιστευτικά και θα ανωνυμοποιηθούν για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς ώστε να αναλυθούν οι τελικοί συμμετέχοντες στο έργο Urban ReLeaf. Η συλλογή τους είναι απαραίτητη για τους ερευνητικούς σκοπούς του έργου και σύνομη με τον Γενικό Κανονισμό για την Προστασία των Δεδομένων (ΓΚΠΔ - GDPR).

Συναίνεση

Αν συναινείτε παρακαλούμε σημειώστε με "X" στις παρακάτω προτάσεις:

- Έχω διαβάσει και κατανοήσει τις λεπτομέρειες της δράσης Urban ReLeaf και συμφωνώ με τη συμμετοχή στην δράση και αναγνωρίζω τους όρους και τις συνθήκες που αναφέρονται στο παρόν έντυπο.
- Συμφωνώ στην δημοσίευση των ερευνητικών αποτελεσμάτων. Σε κανένα στάδιο της έρευνας δεν θα εμφανιστεί/δημοσιευτεί το όνομά μου.

Όνοματεπώνυμο:

Ημερομηνία:

Υπογραφή:

Δημογραφικά στοιχεία

Φύλο:

- Γυναίκα
- Άντρας
- Non-binary
- Άλλο
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

Ηλικιακή κατηγορία:

- Κάτω των 18 ετών
- 19-24 χρονών
- 25-34 χρονών
- 35-44 χρονών
- 45-54 χρονών
- 55-64 χρονών
- 65-74 χρονών
- Άνω των 75 χρονών
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

Επίπεδο σπουδών:

- Απολυτήριο λυκείου
- Πτυχίο ανώτατης εκπαίδευσης
- Μεταπτυχιακό
- Διδακτορικό
- Άλλο
- Καμία εκπαίδευση
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

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Appendix C

Templates of the informed consents of the Trees campaigns referring to the schools implementation. The templates are provided in English and in Greek and are for the school administration and the parent/legal guardian of each student to participate. Also include are anonymized demographics questionnaires.

Consent Form Parent/Legal Guardian

A citizen science activity of the Urban ReLeaf project will be organised at your school. During this activity, pupils will collect environmental observations using new technologies.

Your child will be asked to use a mobile application, namely the Athens Tree App, that maps the trees in the streets of your neighbourhood.

Participation is voluntary and you are free to stop your child's participation in this study at any time.

Below you can find more information about the study and how it will proceed.

Information about the Urban ReLeaf project

Urban ReLeaf (urbanreleaf.eu) is a European project. The project invites citizens to collect environmental observations using new technologies. Together, we develop innovations and new greening policies to fight climate change. Our vision is an inclusive and green transition.

The project is coordinated by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Austria.

In Athens, the project activities will be led and implemented by DAEM. For further information, you can contact: Dimitra Tsakanika, d.tsakanika@daem.gr and Iliia Christantoni, i.christantoni@daem.gr.

Information about the campaign

DAEM will organize the campaign in the school during which the students will be informed about the project, the aim of the study and the use of the application. Then, DAEM will distribute mobiles with the App already installed and the students will be divided in groups. Each group will map the trees in neighbourhood streets according to the division in groups and instructions. The mapping will take place during one school course.

Privacy and confidentiality

The data collected through the technologies during the Urban ReLeaf activities are controlled by CIBOS Innovation Private Company, Zan Moreas 40, 11745, Athens, Greece, info@cibos.gr. The handling of the personal data provided, including anonymization and sharing of anonymized data, with project partners of the Urban ReLeaf for analysis, is managed by DAEM. The data will be kept confidential and will be anonymized for scientific purposes, such as to analyze the participants of the Urban ReLeaf project. This data collection is necessary for the scientific purposes of the Urban ReLeaf project and complies with the requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

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Consent

Please give your consent by marking the boxes with an 'X':

- I have read and understood the details of the Urban ReLeaf study. I agree to allow my child to participate in the study, and I acknowledge the terms and conditions outlined in this consent form.
- I consent to the publication of the research results. Neither my name nor my child's name will be published and the confidentiality of the data is guaranteed at every stage of the research.

Name of the parent(s)/legal guardian(s):

Name of the child:

Date:

Signature:

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Participant form

Gender of the child:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other
- I prefer not to answer

Age of the child:

- Under 16 years old
- Between 16 and 18 years old
- Over 18 years old
- I prefer not to answer

Level of education of the mother:

- Secondary education
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other degree
- No education
- I prefer not to answer

Level of education of the father:

- Secondary education
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other degree
- No education
- I prefer not to answer

Urban ReLeaf has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No.101086638. UK participants in the Urban ReLeaf project are supported by United Kingdom Research and Innovation ("UKRI") Innovate UK under grant agreements 10061290 and 10041792.

Έντυπο Συναίνεσης Γονέα/Κηδεμόνα

Σας ενημερώνουμε ότι θα διοργανωθεί στο σχολείο σας μια δράση επιστήμης των πολιτών στο πλαίσιο του Ευρωπαϊκού έργου Urban ReLeaf. Κατά τη διάρκεια αυτής της δράσης/καμπάνιας, οι μαθητές θα συλλέξουν περιβαλλοντικές παρατηρήσεις χρησιμοποιώντας νέες τεχνολογίες.

Το παιδί σας θα κληθεί να χρησιμοποιήσει μια εφαρμογή για κινητά και συγκεκριμένα το Athens Tree App, που χαρτογραφεί τα δέντρα της γειτονιάς σας.

Η συμμετοχή είναι εθελοντική και είστε ελεύθεροι να διακόψετε τη συμμετοχή του παιδιού σας από αυτήν τη μελέτη/δράση ανά πάσα στιγμή.

Παρακάτω μπορείτε να βρείτε περισσότερες πληροφορίες σχετικά με τη μελέτη και τον τρόπο με τον οποίο θα προχωρήσει.

Πληροφορίες για το Ευρωπαϊκό έργο Urban ReLeaf

Το Urban ReLeaf (urbanreleaf.eu) είναι ένα Ευρωπαϊκό ερευνητικό έργο που προσκαλεί πολίτες να συλλέξουν περιβαλλοντικά δεδομένα και παρατηρήσεις μέσω νέων τεχνολογιών. Στόχος είναι να αναπτυχθούν καινοτόμες δράσεις που θα οδηγήσουν σε νέες πολιτικές για το περιβάλλον ώστε να αντιμετωπιστεί η κλιματική αλλαγή και να επιτευχθεί μια συμπεριληπτική πράσινη μετάβαση.

Συντονιστής του έργου είναι το Διεθνές Ινστιτούτο Ανάλυσης Εφαρμοσμένων Συστημάτων (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Αυστρία.

Στην Αθήνα η πιλοτική εφαρμογή και οι σχετικές δράσεις συντονίζονται από τη ΔΑΕΜ. Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με: Δήμητρα Τσακανίκα, d.tsakanika@daem.gr και Ίλια Χρισταντώνη, i.christantoni@daem.gr.

Πληροφορίες για τη καμπάνια

Η ΔΑΕΜ θα οργανώσει την δράση στο σχολείο κατά τη διάρκεια της οποίας οι μαθητές θα ενημερωθούν για το έργο, το σκοπό της δράσης και τον τρόπο χρήσης της εφαρμογής. Στη συνέχεια, θα τους διαμοιραστούν κινητές συσκευές της ΔΑΕΜ με εγκατεστημένη την εφαρμογή, θα χωριστούν σε ομάδες και κάθε ομάδα θα χαρτογραφήσει δένδρα της γειτονιάς του σχολείου σε συγκεκριμένους δρόμους σύμφωνα με το διαχωρισμό των ομάδων και τις οδηγίες που θα δοθούν. Η δράση θα λάβει χώρα μια διδακτική ώρα.

Ιδιωτικότητα και εμπιστευτικότητα

Urban ReLeaf has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No.101086638. UK participants in the Urban ReLeaf project are supported by United Kingdom Research and Innovation ("UKRI") Innovate UK under grant agreements 10061290 and 10041792.

Τα δεδομένα που συλλέγονται μέσω του Athens Tree App κατά τη διάρκεια των δράσεων ελέγχονται από την CIBOS Innovation Private Company, Ζαν Μωρέα 40, 11745, Αθήνα, Ελλάδα, info@cibos.gr

Για τη διαχείριση των προσωπικών δεδομένων, της ανωνυμοποίησής τους και του διαμοιρασμού μόνο ανωνυμοποιημένων δεδομένων με τους εταίρους του έργου, υπεύθυνη είναι η ΔΑΕΜ.

Τα δεδομένα θα παραμείνουν εμπιστευτικά και θα ανωνυμοποιηθούν για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς ώστε να αναλυθούν οι τελικοί συμμετέχοντες στο έργο Urban ReLeaf. Η συλλογή τους είναι απαραίτητη για τους ερευνητικούς σκοπούς του έργου και σύνομη με το Γενικό Κανονισμό για την Προστασία των Δεδομένων (ΓΚΠΔ - GDPR).

Συναίνεση

Αν συναινείτε παρακαλούμε σημειώστε με "X" στις παρακάτω προτάσεις:

- Έχω διαβάσει και κατανοήσει τις λεπτομέρειες της δράσης στο πλαίσιο του Ευρωπαϊκού έργου Urban ReLeaf. Συμφωνώ με τη συμμετοχή του παιδιού μου στην δράση και αναγνωρίζω τους όρους και τις συνθήκες που αναφέρονται στο παρόν έντυπο.
- Συμφωνώ στην δημοσίευση των ερευνητικών αποτελεσμάτων. Σε κανένα στάδιο της έρευνας δεν θα εμφανιστεί/δημοσιευτεί το όνομά μου, ούτε το όνομα του παιδιού μου.

Όνοματεπώνυμο γονέα/κηδεμόνα:

Όνοματεπώνυμο μαθητή:

Ημερομηνία:

Υπογραφή γονέα/κηδεμόνα:

Δημογραφικά στοιχεία

Φύλο μαθητή:

- Κορίτσι
- Αγόρι
- Non-binary
- Άλλο
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

Ηλικία μαθητή:

- Κάτω των 16 ετών
- 16-18 χρονών
- Άνω των 18 χρονών
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

Επίπεδο σπουδών μητέρας:

- Απολυτήριο λυκείου
- Πτυχίο ανώτατης εκπαίδευσης
- Μεταπτυχιακό
- Διδακτορικό
- Άλλο
- Καμία εκπαίδευση
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

Επίπεδο σπουδών πατέρα:

- Απολυτήριο λυκείου
- Πτυχίο ανώτατης εκπαίδευσης
- Μεταπτυχιακό
- Διδακτορικό
- Άλλο
- Καμία εκπαίδευση
- Δεν επιθυμώ να απαντήσω

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Consent Form School

A citizen science activity of the Urban ReLeaf project will be organised at your school. During this activity, pupils will collect environmental observations using new technologies.

We would like your permission to invite the pupils to take part in the following Urban ReLeaf project activities: the students will be handed over by DAEM mobiles with the Athens Tree Application already installed. Then, the students will be divided in groups and each group will map the trees in neighbourhood streets according to the division in groups and instructions.

For research purposes, we would also like to collect socio-demographic information about the pupils, that is: gender, age, and parental education level. The goal of the Urban ReLeaf project is to provide inclusive activities for all young people. Therefore, the collection of these demographic data allows us to assess the extent to which this is the case.

Participation is voluntary and the school may withdraw participation at any moment.

Below you will find more information about the campaign and how it will be organised.

Information about the Urban ReLeaf project

Urban ReLeaf (urbanreleaf.eu) is a European project. The project invites citizens to collect environmental observations using new technologies. Together, we develop innovations and new greening policies to fight climate change. Our vision is an inclusive and green transition.

The project is coordinated by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Austria.

In Athens, the project activities will be led and implemented by DAEM. For further information, you can contact: Dimitra Tsakanika, d.tsakanika@daem.gr and Ilia Christantoni, i.christantoni@daem.gr.

Information about the campaign

DAEM will organize the campaign in the school during which the students will be informed about the project, the aim of the study and the use of the application. Then, DAEM will distribute mobiles with the App already installed and the students will be divided in groups. Each group will map the trees in neighbourhood streets according to the division in groups and instructions. The mapping will take place during one school course.

Privacy and confidentiality

The data collected through the technologies during the Urban ReLeaf activities are controlled by CIBOS Innovation Private Company, Zan Moreas 40, 11745, Athens, Greece, info@cibos.gr

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The handling of the personal data provided, including anonymization and sharing of anonymized data, with project partners of the Urban ReLeaf for analysis, is managed by DAEM. The data will be kept confidential and will be anonymized for scientific purposes, such as to analyze the participants of the Urban ReLeaf project. This data collection is necessary for the scientific purposes of the Urban ReLeaf project and complies with the requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Consent of the school

Please give your consent by marking the phrase with an 'X':

- I agree to participate in the Urban ReLeaf project

Name of the school:

Main contact of the school:

Date:

Signature:

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Έντυπο Συναίνεσης Σχολείου

Στο σχολείο σας θα λάβει χώρα μια καμπάνια επιστήμης πολιτών (citizen science) του Ευρωπαϊκού ερευνητικού έργου Urban ReLeaf. Κατά τη διάρκεια της καμπάνιας/δράσης οι μαθητές θα συλλέξουν περιβαλλοντικά δεδομένα με τη χρήση νέων τεχνολογιών.

Παρακαλούμε για την συναίνεση και άδειά σας να προσκληθούν μαθητές στην δράση του έργου Urban ReLeaf όπου θα τους διαμοιραστούν συσκευές κινητών με εγκατεστημένη την εφαρμογή Athens Trees App. Οι μαθητές θα την χρησιμοποιήσουν για να χαρτογραφίσουν δένδρα στους δρόμους της γειτονιάς. Θα χωριστούν σε ομάδες και κάθε ομάδα θα χαρτογραφήσει δένδρα σε δρόμους που θα τους υποδειχθούν.

Επιπλέον, για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς θα συλλεχθούν δημογραφικά δεδομένα από τους μαθητές εφόσον επιθυμούν να απαντήσουν: φύλο, ηλικία και επίπεδο εκπαίδευσης γονέων/κηδεμόνων. Στόχος του έργου είναι η διοργάνωση συμπεριληπτικών δράσεων για τους νέους. Συνεπώς, η συλλογή των παραπάνω δημογραφικών θα μας βοηθήσει να αξιολογήσουμε τη συμμετοχή νέων.

Η συμμετοχή είναι εθελοντική και το σχολείο έχει το δικαίωμα να διακόψει τη συμμετοχή του οποιαδήποτε στιγμή.

Παρακάτω παραθέτονται περισσότερες πληροφορίες για την καμπάνια και τη διοργάνωση.

Πληροφορίες για το έργο

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Το έργο συντονίζει το International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Αυστρία.

Στην Αθήνα η πιλοτική εφαρμογή και οι σχετικές δράσεις συντονίζονται από τη ΔΑΕΜ. Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με: Δήμητρα Τσακανικά, d.tsakanika@daem.gr και Ίλια Χρισταντώνη, i.christantonii@daem.gr.

Πληροφορίες για την καμπάνια

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Η ΔΑΕΜ θα οργανώσει την δράση στο σχολείο σας κατά τη διάρκεια της οποίας οι μαθητές θα ενημερωθούν για το έργο, το σκοπό της δράσης και τον τρόπο χρήσης της εφαρμογής. Στη συνέχεια, θα τους διαμοιραστούν κινητές συσκευές της ΔΑΕΜ με εγκατεστημένη την εφαρμογή, θα χωριστούν σε ομάδες και κάθε ομάδα θα χαρτογραφήσει δένδρα της γειτονιάς του σχολείου σε συγκεκριμένους δρόμους σύμφωνα με το διαχωρισμό των ομάδων. Η δράση θα λάβει χώρα μια διδακτική ώρα.

Ιδιωτικότητα και εμπιστευτικότητα

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Συναίνεση σχολείου

Αν συναινείτε παρακαλούμε σημειώστε με "X" στην παρακάτω πρόταση:

- Συμφωνώ με τη συμμετοχή στο έργο Urban ReLeaf

Όνομα σχολείου:

Υπεύθυνος σχολείου:

Ημερομηνία:

Υπογραφή: